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Final recommendations on FAIR-by-Design training resources

M2.4

Authors

Sonja Filiposka, UKIM/T2.3
Anastas Mishev, UKIM/T2.3
Andrea Corleto, GARR/T2.3
Eleonora Napolitano, GARR/T2.3
Gabriella Paolini, GARR/T2.3
Sara di Giorgio, GARR/T2.3
Achim Winandi, KIT/T2.3
Joanna Janik, CNRS/T2.3
Kasper Drazewski, KUL/ELSI
Arnaud Gingold, AMU/T2.3
Christine Hadrossek, CNRS/T2.3
Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, OPERAS/T2.3
Dominique Green, IDCC/WP2
Claudio Prandoni, GARR/Coordinator

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Executive Summary

The FAIR-by-Design Methodology provides a comprehensive framework for the development of learning materials. It offers clear, structured guidance on how to create FAIR training resources while allowing flexibility in the choice of tools, platforms, and content formats.

This milestone presents the final recommendations on FAIR-by-Design training resources, summarizing insights gained through the iterative co-creation and continuous improvement process implemented up to January 2025. The recommendations are focusing on the commonly identified challenges thus far and build upon extensive stakeholder engagement, feedback mechanisms, and hands-on implementation experiences.

The identified common challenges that users may face when applying the methodology include handling closed materials, managing version control, ensuring proper attribution, structuring content for maximum usability, and maintaining the sustainability of published training resources. For each challenge, the document presents practical solutions and recommendations, helping users overcome obstacles and maintain compliance with FAIR principles.

The document also includes key takeaways, summarizing the most important insights for implementing the methodology effectively. It reinforces the idea that FAIR-by-Design is not just a set of rules but a flexible, evolving approach that supports better knowledge sharing and reuse in Open Science.

Future refinements to the methodology will be made as new needs and challenges arise. The methodology is designed to grow and evolve, ensuring that learning materials remain relevant, high-quality, and aligned with the changing landscape of Open Science education.

By following the guidance outlined in this document, instructors, trainers, and learning material developers can create robust, reusable, and widely accessible training content that aligns with best practices in Open Science and digital education.

Introduction

Ensuring that learning materials adhere to the [principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability \(FAIR\)](#) is essential for fostering a culture of open science and knowledge sharing. The FAIR-by-Design Methodology, published in [D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials](#), was developed as a systematic approach to embedding FAIR principles into the instructional design process from the outset, rather than applying them retrospectively. This methodology provides structured guidance for trainers, instructional designers, and educational/training institutions, supporting them in creating, maintaining, and improving learning materials that align with the FAIR principles.

The FAIR-by-Design Methodology is rooted in best practices for instructional design and learning material development. It integrates the [backward instructional design model](#), as one of the widely accepted frameworks in education, with specific FAIR actions at each stage of material creation. This approach ensures that the resulting materials are not only instructionally effective but also fully aligned with FAIR principles, facilitating broader adoption, reuse, and integration into open educational ecosystems.

Within the Skills4EOSC project, the methodology has undergone extensive development and refinement through an iterative, co-creative process involving project partners, external stakeholders, and practitioners. Since its initial conception, it has been validated through internal reviews, public consultations, training sessions, and real-world implementation by early adopters. This milestone documents these efforts, presenting the latest improvements, key lessons learned and recommendations for ensuring the long-term sustainability and usability of FAIR-by-Design training resources.

By documenting the outcomes of the FAIR-by-Design methodology development and refinement process, this milestone serves as a reference for current and future practitioners who wish to integrate FAIR principles into their educational resources in a structured and sustainable manner. It highlights both the successes and challenges encountered, offering actionable insights for improving and expanding the methodology's impact across various scientific and educational communities.

Furthermore, the continuous improvement process for the FAIR-by-Design methodology and its associated training resources will remain an ongoing effort until the end of the Skills4EOSC project. As new insights emerge from continued training sessions, real-world implementations, and collaborations with external stakeholders, the methodology will be further refined to address evolving needs and challenges. Additional feedback is expected from ongoing and future training activities, including postmortem analyses from teams applying the methodology in practice. Moreover, as more institutions and projects express interest in adopting FAIR-by-Design, their experiences and contributions will provide valuable input for future enhancements. This iterative refinement ensures that the methodology remains dynamic, relevant, and fully aligned with the principles of open science, ultimately supporting a growing community of practitioners dedicated to the creation of FAIR learning materials.

Continuous improvement Process

The FAIR-by-Design Methodology, which provides a structured approach for integrating FAIR principles into the development of learning materials, was designed to benefit both learners and trainers, ensuring that educational resources are not only accessible to learners but also findable, interoperable, and reusable for all. To achieve this, the methodology builds upon best practices in instructional design and incorporates key FAIR principles into the widely accepted backward instructional design framework. The result is a six-stage process that guides content creators from the ideation phase through to publication, verification, and continuous improvement. These stages are captured in a nutshell in the now well-known graphical representation of the methodology.

Recognizing that openness and collaboration are fundamental aspects of FAIR learning materials, the FAIR-by-Design Methodology was not developed in isolation. Instead, from its inception, the methodology has been subject to a co-creation process, ensuring that it reflects the collective expertise of the open science and instructional design communities. In collaboration with Task 6, this process was structured in multiple phases of review, feedback gathering, and iterative improvement, ensuring that the methodology remains responsive to the needs of the training community.

Initial Development and Project-Wide Consultation

The first step in this co-creation journey was an extensive internal review within the Skills4EOSC consortium. Upon completing the initial draft, the T2.3 team conducted a structured internal revision, ensuring that the methodology was aligned with the goals of Skills4EOSC and incorporated state-of-the-art best practices.

Following this internal validation, a project-wide consultation phase was initiated. During this phase the draft methodology was shared with all Skills4EOSC partner institutions, enabling early engagement from a diverse group of stakeholders. A dedicated webinar was organized at the project level, providing an opportunity to present the methodology, explain its rationale, and invite discussion on potential improvements. Feedback collected from project partners was systematically analysed and integrated into a revised version of the methodology.

This first phase of review and revision resulted in an [official draft of the FAIR-by-Design Methodology](#), incorporating insights from domain experts within the Skills4EOSC consortium. Up to 2025 the official deliverable has been seen over 2K times on Zenodo and has had over 1K downloads.

Community Engagement and Public Feedback

To expand the validation process beyond the project consortium, the revised methodology was [published on Zenodo](#), making it openly available for broader consultation. It was accompanied by an EC Survey, allowing external researchers, educators, and instructional designers to provide structured feedback.

This phase ensured that the methodology was scrutinized by a wider audience, including external stakeholders, open science practitioners, and training experts. The responses collected from the survey were carefully analysed, and the methodology was further refined to address identified gaps and improve clarity. The revised version was then transformed into an [official deliverable](#), subjected to internal peer review, and finalized for public release.

Establishing Continuous Feedback Loops

Understanding that the FAIR-by-Design Methodology must remain dynamic and adaptable (as it is suggested in the methodology itself), the T2.3 team established multiple feedback channels to continuously gather input from both internal and external users. These channels include:

1. [Permanent EC Survey Form](#) – The original EC survey remains open, allowing ongoing collection of public opinions regarding the methodology.
2. Feedback Forms in Training Programs – All training sessions, including the flagship [FAIR-by-Design Training of Trainers \(ToT\) course](#), incorporate dedicated feedback forms to capture participant insights.
3. Public GitHub Issues and Discussions – All FAIR-by-Design Methodology materials are hosted on public GitHub repositories, where users can submit feedback, suggestions, and requests for improvements via the Issues feature.

4. [Fork and Pull Contribution Mechanism](#) – Since all methodology materials are openly licensed, any user can fork the repositories and propose direct modifications via pull requests, fostering community-driven improvements.
5. Postmortem Documentation – In collaboration with T2.6, a structured postmortem process has been established to gather detailed reflections from teams that have applied the methodology in real-world instructional design projects.
6. Direct Communication Channels – All materials provide clear instructions on how users can directly contact the T2.3 team to seek guidance or propose enhancements.

Feedback Driven Refinement and Versioning

The continuous improvement process is data-driven, ensuring that changes to the methodology and related resources are based on real-world user experiences. As of January 2025, the FAIR-by-Design team has received:

- 70+ feedback responses from participants on training sessions and workshops,
- 15 postmortem reports detailing the experiences of both internal and external adopters,
- 47 survey responses from the ongoing EC surveys,
- 22 responses to the Training of Trainers feedback survey,
- 12 GitHub issues with improvement suggestions,
- Over 50 forks of the public repositories,
- Numerous direct emails and inquiries regarding methodology implementation.

From the gathered feedback, continuous improvement items have been developed, each with corresponding priority and impact level. The items have then been implemented by the team in the main outputs related to the methodology.

Major Improvements Implemented

Several key enhancements to the methodology have resulted from this continuous improvement process, including:

- Multimedia Integration – Expanded guidance on incorporating videos and other media into FAIR learning materials.
- FAIR Signposting – Collaboration with FAIR IMPACT led to improvements in machine-readability of learning materials.
- Tool-Agnostic Implementation – New microlearning units and templates for users unfamiliar with GitHub and Markdown.
- Interactive Navigation – Creation of an interactive FAIR-by-Design map to facilitate easier access to relevant resources.
- Guidance for Closed Materials – New documentation on how to apply FAIR principles to learning materials with restricted access.

- Workshops on Licensing and Reuse – Dedicated training on how to legally reuse existing educational resources under open licenses.
- Development of a methodology guidebook – a short reference guide on how to practically implement the FAIR-by-Design methodology.

To ensure transparency and traceability, the T2.3 team has implemented a release notes system across all FAIR-by-Design web-based resources. This system enables recurring users to track updates and understand the specific changes introduced in each new version of the methodology. For a more detailed overview of improvements and updates, users can refer to the release notes of each of the materials.

In the next section of this document, we address the main challenges that have been identified during the continuous improvement process. These challenges serve as final recommendations from the T2.3 team that should help future FAIR-by-Design practitioners implement the methodology with confidence and produce high quality learning materials.

Main FAIR-by-Design Methodology Outputs

The following is a list of the main FAIR-by-Design Methodology Outputs that are being continuously updated using the process described above:

- [FAIR-by-Design Methodology Gitbook](#) – an online up-to-date version of the FAIR-by-Design Methodology deliverable;
- [FAIR-by-Design Methodology Training of Trainers](#) – self-paced training on practical implementation of the methodology;
- [FAIR-by-Design Methodology Microlearning Unit](#) – interactive ultra short learning unit on how to implement the methodology;
- [FAIR-by-Design Methodology Templates](#) – start up repository that can be forked to get a jump start on practical implementation;
- [FAIR-by-Design Methodology Guidebook](#) – newest addition, a quick how to use guide in a PDF format.

In addition to these, the team has also published tailored training materials, such as the [training for the CLARIN-ERIC community](#), as well as success stories by adopters outside the consortium, such as the [implementation success story for the DoRANum learning platform](#). The microlearning unit has also been adapted and published as a draft course for the Galaxy Project Training Platform.

Ensuring Long-Term Sustainability

As the Skills4EOSC project progresses, the continuous improvement process will remain a central priority. Ongoing training activities, future collaborations, and new methodology adopters will provide additional insights, which will be systematically collected, analysed, and integrated into future updates. The methodology will continue to be refined in alignment with emerging best practices, ensuring that it remains a living resource that evolves alongside the needs of the open education and research communities.

Beyond the Skills4EOSC project, efforts will be made to sustain the methodology through institutional adoption, collaborations with related initiatives, and integration into long-term open science training frameworks. By maintaining a strong commitment to openness, transparency, and responsiveness, the FAIR-by-Design Methodology will continue to empower educators and researchers to create and share FAIR learning resources for years to come.

Overcoming common challenges

While the FAIR-by-Design (FbD) methodology provides a structured approach to creating and sharing learning materials, implementing it effectively comes with its own set of challenges. Below, we address some of the most frequently encountered issues and provide recommendations and guidance on overcoming them. These challenges have been identified using the described co-creation process for continuous improvement and were mostly raised by the FbD practitioners in their postmortem reports. For each of the challenges, we map the stage of the methodology it refers to as well as the FAIR principle it is related to.

1. Are the tools and platforms used in the ToT course mandatory?

The FbD methodology is designed to be platform- and tool-agnostic. The tools and platforms mentioned in the materials serve as examples and best practices rather than requirements. Authors of learning materials are free to select the tools and platforms that best suit their needs, provided they maintain the FAIRness of the produced learning content.

2. How to publish closed FAIR learning materials?

Some learning materials cannot be openly shared due to financial, legal, or institutional constraints. The FbD methodology acknowledges these limitations and provides strategies to enhance the FAIRness of closed materials. One effective approach is to provide detailed metadata, ensuring that the material remains fully findable, and its existence known. This means that the syllabus (which is based on the RDA minimal metadata schema) with all necessary, searchable, information and access conditions should be clearly documented and provided openly. In this way, potential users can determine whether they are eligible to access the material and under what conditions.

3. Are slides alone sufficient as provided learning materials?

The simple, short answer is No. Extensive research and experience in learning material development indicate that slides alone do not constitute a complete learning package. While slides are valuable for face-to-face teaching and webinars, they lack the necessary context to be fully FAIR. Without supporting materials such as speaker notes, transcripts, exercises, or explanations, slides are difficult to reuse effectively. The main identified challenge with slides is their reusability. Using someone else's slides without any supporting documents can represent a big challenge. FbD recommends complementing slides with additional documentation to improve reusability and ensure both learners and trainers can engage with the material independently.

4. I'm preparing an online course, does the methodology apply?

The FbD methodology applies equally well to online learning materials. When creating digital resources, authors should ensure that content is structured for accessibility, tagged with proper metadata, and formatted to support easy discovery and reuse. Even for self-paced courses, elements like an instructor's guide can be beneficial, providing hosting platforms and courses administrators with context on the best way to structure and present the course.

5. When to create a new version, when to fork and create a new learning object?

Proper versioning is essential for maintaining transparency and ensuring users can track changes to learning materials. The FbD methodology recommends:

- Major versions for significant structural or content changes.
- Minor versions for smaller modifications or clarifications.
- Patch updates for technical fixes or minor corrections.

Each version should be accompanied by clear release notes, enabling users to understand what has changed and whether updates affect their intended use of the material.

One should strive to create a new learning object based on an old one in the case when there are significant changes regarding the items defined in the Prepare stage:

- Substantial changes in learning objectives
- Changed target audience
- Change in prerequisites

6. What if there is no licence attached to a material I want to reuse?

If a resource does not have a license attached, it should not be assumed that it is free to be reused. The FbD methodology advises reaching out to the original creator or institution for inquiry and clarification. If usage rights remain unclear, alternative resources with explicit licensing should be considered. Proper licensing is fundamental to ensuring legal and ethical reuse.

7. What are the bare minimum elements to be FAIR-by-Design?

To align with FbD principles, the following elements are essential:

- (F) Comprehensive metadata to enhance findability.
- (F) PID of the published learning object with editable content for instructors.
- (A) Learning object is checked for accessibility aiming for wide audience.
- (A) Access rules to learning object are clearly stated.
- (I) Metadata schema (min RDA or compatible) is used
- (I) A structured format of the learning object that supports interoperability and reusability using open file formats.
- (R) Clear licensing information to ensure legal reuse.
- (R) Clear attribution of reused work, if any.

Beyond these, additional elements—such as documentation, version history, and open co-creation considerations can improve FAIRness.

8. Can I deviate from the proposed structure in the templates?

The FbD methodology provides a guiding framework rather than a rigid structure. Learning material authors are encouraged to adapt the methodology to their specific needs. The proposed structure serves to make materials more FAIR, but authors can modify it as long as their changes still uphold the core FAIR principles.

9. Can I claim sole authorship when combining reused resources?

No. When combining content from multiple existing courses into a new one, it's essential to accurately attribute the original authors. Claiming sole authorship without acknowledging the contributions of others would be misleading and unethical. Proper attribution not only respects the original creators but also maintains the integrity and transparency of the educational resources.

10. What is the difference between adapted and remixed content?

Distinguishing between adapted and remixed content is crucial for proper attribution and licensing.

- Adapted content involves making modifications to existing material to better fit a specific context. You must follow the CC adapter license guidelines.
- Remixed content combines elements from multiple sources to create something new. You can remix different CC licenses together.

Understanding this distinction helps in applying appropriate licenses and providing accurate attributions, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.

11. Does my learning object licence apply to all reused content?

No. The license you attach to your content applies only to the material you have created/adapted. When reusing and remixing external resources, their original licenses remain in effect. This is why when applying your license, it is best if it starts with the text "Except where otherwise noted, this content is licensed under [your license]."

12. Why is a Code of Conduct important?

Learning materials developed under the FbD methodology often involve contributions from diverse participants. A Code of Conduct ensures respectful collaboration, setting clear expectations for behaviour of all relevant parties and addressing potential conflicts. This is particularly crucial when enabling public contributions, as it helps mitigate issues such as inappropriate comments or non-academic disputes.

13. Do I have to use Zenodo to publish the learning materials?

No. Zenodo is a widely used FAIR repository, making it a strong choice for sharing learning materials. However, it is not mandatory for use. The key requirement is to choose a platform that ensures findability, accessibility, and long-term preservation. Zenodo simplifies discoverability by centralizing FAIR-compliant educational resources, but alternative repositories can be used if they provide similar benefits.

14. Do I have to use GitHub as collaboration platform?

No. While GitHub offers a structured and transparent way to collaborate with version control, issue tracking, contribution transparency, and integration with Zenodo it is not a mandatory requirement. However, the key is to choose a collaboration platform that ensures transparency, versioning, proper licensing, and metadata enrichment.

15. How long does it take to fully develop FbD learning materials?

FbD introduces a structured process that can initially seem time-consuming, especially for new users. However, once familiar with the methodology, material development becomes more efficient. The structured approach helps streamline creation while ensuring compliance with FAIR principles. From our own experience, when the learning content developers becomes more familiar with FbD, the development time can be reduced.

16. Can I use the methodology to make my materials FAIR later, after my deadline?

Delaying the FAIR implementation can be risky. While it is possible to improve FAIRness post-publication, it is significantly easier to integrate FAIR principles from the start. Retrofitting materials may require additional effort to add metadata, restructure content, and clarify licensing. Incorporating FAIR principles early reduces the risk of non-compliance and ensures long-term usability.

17. How to ensure long term sustainability of the learning materials?

Sustainability is a key challenge for all learning materials. To ensure materials remain available and up to date:

- Choose repositories with long-term support and maintenance.
- Use versioning to track updates.
- Clearly document the creation date and last review date.
- Build a strong co-creation community.
- Establish a process for regular review and updates, assigning responsibility for maintaining content.

Without proper upkeep, outdated materials can mislead learners rather than benefit them.

Key takeaways

FAIR-by-Design is flexible, not prescriptive

The methodology provides guidance rather than rigid rules, allowing creators to adapt structures, tools, and platforms to fit their needs while ensuring that learning materials remain FAIR.

Metadata and documentation are as important as the content itself

Well-structured metadata, licensing information, and supporting documentation make learning materials more discoverable and reusable, ensuring that their value extends beyond their initial context.

FAIR is about responsible and sustainable sharing

While openness is encouraged, the methodology recognizes that some materials must remain restricted. It provides clear guidance on how to maintain FAIR principles even when materials cannot be fully open.

Interoperability ensures long-term usability

By adopting open formats and standard structures, learning materials can be used across platforms, disciplines, and educational settings without losing their integrity or usefulness.

The process of making materials FAIR is iterative and continuous

Designing FAIR learning materials is not a one-time effort. Continuous updates, versioning, and improvements based on user feedback are necessary to maintain relevance and usability.

FAIR-by-Design fosters collaboration and co-creation

The methodology encourages co-creation and knowledge-sharing, enabling a diverse range of contributors to improve and adapt educational content for different audiences and contexts.

Attribution and licensing are vital for ethical and legal reuse

Proper attribution ensures that original creators receive recognition, while clear licensing prevents misuse and enables broader adoption of materials.

The instructor kit enhances both face-to-face and online education

The methodology supports diverse learning environments, ensuring that both in-person and digital training materials are well-organized, comprehensive, and reusable.

Modular design enhances adaptability

By structuring learning resources into self-contained, reusable units instead of large monolithic files, you provide small, independent learning objects that can easily be mixed and matched.

Minimal technical barriers improve access

By avoid requiring proprietary software and paying attention to provide both final and editable source files, users can access and modify content easily.

Versioning matters

Maintaining clear version histories, distinguishing between major and minor updates, and providing release notes help keep learning materials transparent and up to date.

Attribution is non-negotiable

When reusing or remixing materials, proper credit must be given to original creators. Ethical reuse fosters trust and academic integrity.

Conclusion

The FAIR-by-Design Methodology provides a structured and practical framework for developing training materials that align with the FAIR principles. Rather than imposing rigid rules, it offers flexible guidance that allows instructors and training developers to create resources that are not only high-quality and structured but also sustainable and widely applicable across different domains and platforms.

By embedding FAIR principles from the outset, the methodology ensures that learning materials are more than just learning content, they become living resources that can be discovered, adapted, and reused by others over time. Through careful attention to metadata, versioning, licensing, and structured documentation, materials developed with this approach are positioned for long-term impact.

The methodology also acknowledges the real-world challenges faced by those creating and maintaining training resources. From handling closed materials and managing licensing constraints to ensuring that materials remain up to date and relevant, the approach provides concrete strategies for overcoming obstacles while maintaining compliance with FAIR principles. Additionally, it promotes a collaborative and community-driven approach to learning material development, ensuring that knowledge remains open, dynamic, and adaptable.

Ultimately, the FAIR-by-Design Methodology is an evolving process, continuously refined through practice, user feedback, and technological advancements. The commitment to continuous improvement means that as new needs, challenges, and best practices emerge, the methodology will adapt to meet them, ensuring that FAIR learning materials remain relevant, impactful, and aligned with the evolving landscape of Open Science and education.

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